

TOWARDS UNDERSTANDING IDENTIFICATION, SELECTION AND APPRAISAL IN CONTEMPORARY DIGITAL PRESERVATION PRACTICE

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Abstract – Identification, selection and appraisal are key digital preservation activities when ingesting data objects for long-term preservation. This paper describes the approach taken to a major new global survey by the EOSC EDEN project, designed to improve understanding of current practices in this area, and the frameworks, standards and guidelines that support digital preservation professional professionals when tackling these challenges. We situate the survey work in its wider context, outline our approach to question-building and analysis, and share what we hope our findings will tell us.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Regardless of which lifecycle model, conceptual framework or workflow is used by a digital preservation organisation, there is always a point at which data objects officially enter the digital preservation environment. However, these frameworks and models often do not clearly outline how, when and what criteria the decision to preserve that data is based upon. In addition, the term used to describe this decision process may be dependent on the domain in which the archive is embedded.

Three terms commonly used for this process are: identification, selection, and appraisal.

A key standard in the digital preservation domain for this process is the Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard (PAIMAS) [1], which is maintained by the same Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) working group who also maintains the OAIS (Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System) [2]. The PAIMAS standard therefore builds on OAIS concepts and terminology. The PAIMAS process starts with the identification of the contact person(s) on the data producing organisation and ends with the archive reporting back the receipt and validation results of the materials to be deposited to the data producer. The process of deciding whether a digital object is to be preserved in the archive is described as step “P-3 Identify the Content Information to be preserved”. Steps following this are the identification of complementary information (P-5), of the designated community (P-6) and the definition of consumer access to the information (P-7). No extensive detail on how the identification process is to be designed is given within the standard, which points out that “This depends on the context, the information to be archived and those involved” and that a refined definition is “the responsibility of the Producer and the Archive” [1]. PAIMAS does not use the terms ‘appraisal’ or ‘selection’ for this process.

While PAIMAS uses the generic term 'identification', library and archive domains more commonly use the terms 'appraisal' and 'selection', while appraisal processes are especially common in the archival domain. The Society of American Archivists describes appraisal as "the process of determining whether records and other materials have permanent (archival) value" [3]. Examples given for criteria to be considered are provenance/content, authenticity/reliability, order/completeness, condition/cost to preserve and intrinsic value.

The International Council on Archives (ICA) includes the above SAA definition in its Multilingual Archival Terminology (MAT) [4], but it is interesting to note that the translation of 'appraisal' into other languages is specific to the context in which it is used. MAT also includes an entry for 'selection', which is defined as "The process of identifying materials to be preserved because of their enduring value, especially those materials to be physically transferred to an archive" [5].

The CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repository Requirements [6] describe the decision-making process in R08 "Deposit and Appraisal", pointing out that this covers the "selection criteria applied at the point of deposit". The requirement description clearly points to collection development policies or procedures and to the mission/collection profile as input criteria for this decision-making process, but also to preferred file formats. While appraisal and selection are used somewhat interchangeably, identification has a different meaning within the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, where it is used in the context of discovery (R12) and persistent identifiers. What is interesting about the CoreTrustSeal definition of appraisal is that it takes both content and technical quality of the digital object into consideration.

As seen through the examples of PAIMAS, ICA MAT/SAA and CoreTrustSeal, the terms 'identification', 'selection' and 'appraisal' are all used to describe the decision process of what is to be preserved within the archive. These practices are key elements of digital preservation practice for any size of organisation, particularly when the data objects are intended for long-term data preservation, with

the funding commitment and responsibility that implies. But how do on-the-job digital preservation professionals approach these key activities? Which standards, guidelines and frameworks do they refer to when engaged in identification, selection and appraisal of data objects? What levels of quality are measured and how? Can these quality metrics be used for re-appraisal processes along the lifecycle if data is not to be stored for the long-term? And what does "long-term" mean anyway?

The newly initiated European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) project, 'Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level' (EDEN) [7] is a three-year (2025-2027) research initiative funded by the EU Horizon Europe programme [8], that aims to tackle these (amongst many other) questions. The project specifically targets research data archives and addresses the questions of how data quality for digital preservation can be defined, and how this definition can be used in decision-making processes for ongoing preservation. A first step within this work is a global survey to understand how the community conducts these decision-making processes for digital preservation.

In this paper, we introduce the context, goal and methodology of this EDEN survey activity. It is worth noting that this work is very current: by the time of the 2025 iPres conference, we will be able to provide an overview of our initial findings in the hope that community feedback may generate helpful new ways to approach our investigation and to better understand how we currently identify, select, and appraise for preservation. For now, however, our discussion focuses on our planned approach to investigation. By sharing the process behind the survey methodology and content, we aim to engage the wider community in thinking about digital preservation considerations behind identification, selection and appraisal processes.

II. SURVEY CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES

Of the EOSC EDEN project's five Work Packages, WP1 ('Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation') is responsible for leading analysis of the current digital preservation landscape. We employ desk research and survey methods to evaluate existing frameworks, guidelines

and practices for the identification, selection, and appraisal of data for digital preservation. The survey described here is a key part of this work. The results of the survey will ultimately be published as project deliverable 'D1.1 Overview of Identification, Selection and Appraisal Practices for Long-Term Data Preservation', in December 2025. This report will summarise existing appraisal practices across different domains and identify so-called 'moving targets' in the form of selection criteria that change over time.

EDEN WP2 ('Long-term Access and Preservation Services and Tools') will also use the findings of the WP1 survey by turning requirements identified from landscape analysis into systems specifications for a registry and services to help automate curation and preservation actions.

In addition, our efforts will be extended by the analysis of discipline-specific requirements and needs by EDEN WP3 ('Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use'), through further desk research and targeted interviewing. Our deliverable will also include a selection of practices that will be used by EDEN WP4 ('Expert and Community Engagement') for dissemination and engagement of key stakeholders.

At the time of writing, a couple of survey questions are being fine-tuned, but the questioning approach is broadly in place, as follows:

1. Descriptive information (as discussed more fully in section IV, below).
2. Familiarity with frameworks and guidelines for appraisal, identification and selection of data for long-term preservation: a list of well-established frameworks and guidelines are presented. The respondent indicates how familiar they are with each and can list any further reference or guidance resources that they use.
3. Definition of "long-term" preservation: the respondent is asked whether their organisation has a working or agreed definition of this and if so, the source of this definition. If they are working without

an agreed definition, the respondent is invited to report why this is the case.

4. Pathways of data into the archive: the respondent is asked how digital objects enter the organisation for long-term preservation. Choices include self-deposit on a voluntary basis, mandated deposit such as legal or funder mandated deposit, proactive collection building such as harvesting or classical collection building in libraries, and/or third-party data preservation on a contractual level.
5. Practices in assessment of quality of data objects at ingest: the respondent is offered the choice of various aspects of data objects (technical quality, content/information quality, quality of technical metadata, quality of descriptive metadata, quality of administrative metadata). For each aspect, the respondent can specify the types of quality assessment undertaken. There is a further question on the frequency of reassessment.
6. How long digital objects are initially preserved.
7. What happens to digital objects after the agreed initial preservation period.
8. Discipline-specific questions submitted by EDEN WP3 on requirements including metadata standards used, file formats preferred, handling of sensitive data, risks, and community needs, all with a discipline-specific lens.

III. SURVEY METHODOLOGY: CONSIDERATIONS

There were several considerations that guided our initial approach to construction of the survey. As can be seen from this contextualisation, above, the survey had to be carefully designed to accommodate several different desired uses of the information that will be gathered. It was also important to clearly define the intended recipients of the survey. To deal with these issues, we made several deliberate decisions in our approach.

Firstly, messaging about and within the survey is intended to be in as clear and direct language as possible, with our best attempt to avoid discipline-specific language or unnecessary technical terms. We hope that this approach aids understanding and also makes translation of the questions (and later of the findings) as straightforward as possible, where this is required.

Also, our survey is designed to be used across the research, cultural heritage, and industry sectors, so it was also necessary to ensure that our language is as sector-neutral as possible.

In addition, the survey is designed for all those working within the digital preservation organisational context, whether at senior management, middle management, or practitioner levels [9]. During the initial promotion of the survey, we aim to receive responses from as many organisations as possible. However, if we do receive responses from more than one staff level within same organisation, this will add richness to our analysis. Our choice of language aims to accommodate these various staff levels.

Further, although we are European and grateful to be funded by the European Union, we recognise that digital preservation activity is global. We did not wish to design out any opportunity for responses from beyond Europe, in addition to responses from European colleagues. Equally we aim to make our reporting and the understanding that we gained from this activity to be as easily available to a global audience as possible. These considerations also affected our choice of language.

The EU Survey platform will be used for this online survey. This platform was chosen due to the acceptability of its data security arrangements, its appropriateness of fit with our funder, its translation functionality (with twenty-four European languages available) and its affordability.

IV. APPROACH TO DATA ANALYSIS

At the time of writing this proposal (April 2025), the survey questionnaire is undergoing its final testing and refinement prior to release; accordingly, at this stage we clearly cannot provide an overview of survey findings. However, if this paper is accepted, we will have survey data to report upon by

the time of the iPRES conference in November 2025, plus an overview of our analysis, into the contents of the current paper. We strongly anticipate that these findings will spark lively discussion and this in turn will help us to set our findings into a wider context which will improve our final reporting - both for the project and for the wider digital preservation community.

However, at this point in time, we can discuss our intended approach to analysis of the survey data, and the considerations involved in this part of the work.

A. *First round of coding: descriptive*

As soon as results begin to come in, we will begin the first phase, "descriptive coding" [10]. This is the entry - or in our case, checking - of descriptive information about each 'case' or respondent. This allows us to understand, for example, geographical coverage and whether any of the respondents are connected to the same organisation as each other.

In our survey, we ask for a range of descriptive data points including:

- Organisation type chosen from a controlled list produced during the project kick-off meeting;
- Country of organisation chosen from the UN country list [11] plus an option for "other"; size of organisation, chosen from EU classification of organisation size [12];
- The respondent's role within the organisation, chosen from the Library of Congress Digital Preservation Outreach and Education (DPOE) staff levels list [8];
- The discipline area, if any, of digital objects held in the respondent's collection, chosen from the UNESCO Fields of Research and Development taxonomy (FORD) developed by the UN system [13].

B. *Second round of coding: topic*

Responses are then analysed for topics that occur in each response. We can use topic coding [9] to identify themes within and across responses by looking at the selections made from structured responses in combination with information submitted through free text fields. By carefully choosing structured lists of answer options, in

collaboration with in-project digital preservationists, we have limited the scope for the respondent to supply a lot of unstructured ('free') text, in order to keep the analysis as simple as possible. However, a likely maximum of nineteen free text fields remain. (The exact number depends upon the questioning route taken by the respondent.) This means that topic coding will be helpful to our analysis.

C. *Third round of coding: analytical*

In analytical coding, we are looking for topics from round two (topic coding) that occur across our responses, and what conclusions we can start to come to on that basis. For example, do many respondents indicate uncertainty about the definition of 'long term'? And if, so, do those respondents mostly come from a given size or type of organisation? Here we "move up from the data" [14] and move toward forming well-founded findings.

D. *Checking for Credibility, Transferability, Dependability and Confirmability*

Lincoln and Guba [14] introduced the notions of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability as appropriate measures to check the quality of qualitative findings. Credibility indicates confidence in the 'truth' of the findings; Transferability shows that the findings have applicability in other contexts; Dependability demonstrates that the findings are consistent and could be repeated; and Confirmability is the degree of neutrality or the extent to which the study findings are shaped by the respondents and not researcher bias, motivation, or interest [15].

In our analysis, 'credibility' is related to the idea of internal validity. Triangulation is a useful approach here. Our survey includes triangulation questions; for example, we ask the respondent whether their organisation has an agreed or working definition of what 'long-term' means to their organisation, expressed as a number of years. A later question asks the respondent to report how long they initially preserve digital objects that have been selected for "long-term" digital preservation. The responses to these two questions can be cross-referenced to assess the credibility of the response.

In order to consider transferability, we have taken care to use language that avoids sector-

specific, staff level-specific, or discipline-specific specialisation, as far as possible.

When considering dependability, we have structured questions and response options in order to allow a range of different respondent types (i.e. from different sectors, roles and staff levels) to comfortably complete the survey questions. To this end, we have included an "Other" option to every list where appropriate, to encourage the respondent to supply the information that they feel is required, even if they cannot find an appropriate option in the structured range of answers available. We have also supplied "I don't know" response options where appropriate. We would not want the respondent's inability to answer one particular question to deter them from completing the whole questionnaire. Equally, we do not want to respondent to fill in inaccurate information simply in order to complete the survey. These efforts to assist the respondent throughout the questionnaire help to encourage higher reliability of their responses. Other measures include labelling of questions where additional instruction may be useful. We also supported dependability by running a small test pilot with trusted partners before the general release of the online survey.

Confirmability is supported by having different members of the Work Package undertake sample analyses, in order to compare results.

By attending to these measures, our aim is to produce high quality findings that will provide a solid basis for our analysis in WP1, genuine value to the other EDEN work packages and, most importantly, useful insight to the wider digital preservation community.

V. CONCLUSION

Through the survey activity described here, we aim to gather insights from the global digital preservation community on several key aspects of identification, selection, and appraisal, which are both of interest in themselves, and also likely to affect other areas of digital preservation practice. We hope to better understand:

- Which quality aspects are currently checked (and if there's a stronger leaning towards content

quality or towards technical quality depending on institution type);

- If there is a shared definition of 'long-term';

- How the organisations who define 'long-term' as a shorter period – for example less than 10 years – approach quality checks, and succession planning for these data objects.

Findings in these areas will suggest future avenues for investigation. Throughout, we are keen to gather feedback from international data curation, digital preservation and research data management communities on our work. We hope this survey activity, including an account of our proposed approach to data-gathering, question design and analysis, provides insight into the scope of this investigation and the quality of findings that we will share. At the iPRES conference, we will also be able to share headline findings from our survey data and any lessons learned from carrying out this investigation, for feedback from the community.

The EOSC EDEN project will support the digital preservation community and contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) through efforts to better understand current digital preservation practice and to provide appropriate guidance and resources to the community. This includes the survey described here, designed to better understand current identification, appraisal, and selection practices when dealing with the ingest of data objects, and the reference materials that digital preservation professionals currently use to guide them.

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